

Passionate Preference and Purchase Behaviour of Pasteurized Milk products in Virudhunagar District

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Abstract

Milk is an essential commodity in the life of Indian consumers. They prefer healthy and energy drinks for consumption. The main challenge for marketers is, to create the consumer loyalty by quality, freshness, odour and taste. Marketers need to know the consumers response towards their own brand milk and dairy product of its availability, acceptability and affordability.

Today, almost all the people are consuming milk and milk products. Brand preferences of the rural and urban consumers are differ. Some buyers are totally brand loyal, buying only one brand in a product group. Most of the buyers switch over to other brands. A lot of brands of milk products are available in the market. But the consumers prefer a particular brand which is much affordable to them. In the modern business world, due to the development of science and technology, many new brands have been introduced in different technical term wise classification of products in the market every year. The present study has been taken to find out the Brand Preference of Packed Milk among Rural and Urban Consumers.

Keywords: Packed Milk, Pasteurized milk, Consumer behavior.

Introduction

Today's marketer is keen to closely monitor the changes, especially to keep regular track of the changing pattern of consumer's aspirations and competitive actions. Any business success ultimately depends on what consumers choose to do. With a rising awareness of brands, the discerning buyer is choosier. Studies on Consumer behaviour have become increasingly important as the consumers are becoming more heterogeneous and discerning. A firm must understand the buyer the buyer behaviour, his/her preference in favour of one brand or product, what motivates him or her to select a brand or product and who influences him or her to buy the brand or product.

Milk is an indispensable item of consumption for human beings. Man and milk animal lived in proximity and their relationship dates back to the origin of civilisation. Prior to urbanisation, the usual practice was to consume milk in its fresh form or after simple processing. The extra milk was converted into short-term conserved products or puddings that were consumed in a phased and leisurely

manner. Milk gets an important place in the human dietary system. The consumers play a vital role in the marketing of dairy milk. Marketing of fluid milk is different when compared to other consumer goods. Several factors influence the consumers in buying the milk.

Review of Literature

A review of literature places a research study in its proper perspective by showing the amount of work already carried out in the related areas of the study. The following are the studies, which enabled the researcher to undertake this study. Studies on consumer behaviour exclusively in fluid milk in Indian context are scanty. Hence, studies on milk and milk products in India and also in abroad are briefly reviewed here.

Naveen Venkata Prasanna¹ (2003) Purity, taste, thickness, availability, price, service of agents and place of purchase were the criteria used in the study. Attributes like availability, price, and service of agents were also rated good. Other milk brands like Arokya and Amritha rated best for its purity and taste respectively. For all the brands price and service of the agents were rated least.

Paramashivaiah and Arvind Kulkarni² (2003) Education of the respondents had greater influence on preferring pasteurized milk than the illiterates who never used pasteurized milk. It was suggested that the suppliers of pasteurized milk should introduce small packs (say 250 ml) in rural areas and lower the price of their best quality milk i.e. Full cream milk, to make it more affordable for the poor rural consumers because non-users of pasteurized milk identified price as a big hindrance in their purchases. Most of these studies had focused mainly on the consumer awareness of milk types and its fat contents, preference and perception about milk.

Prabhakar Sharma and Joglekar³ (2002) The supply of milk through polyethylene sachets by home delivery was advantageous. The families expressed that the milk supplied by the GCD's is of medium quality. The quality of the milk was primarily judged on the basis of level of fat content in milk. Families belonging to lower income groups strongly expressed their preference to private vendors due to non-availability of milk in small packing less than half a liter.

Suriya Murthi⁴ (2001) in his article on milk marketing strategies had listed some basic components of marketing strategies such as adherence to regulatory standards of quality; supply of hygienic and unadulterated milk. It was suggested that co-operatives to form business alliance with other co-operatives and private companies so as to leverage operational synergy and fair and equitable competition among dairy industry to create competitive advantage.

Filling the Research gap

It is clear from the above discussion that, the previous studies have not concentrated on pasteurized milk products by the different type of milk suppliers in Virudhunagar District. The present study on "Passionate preference purchase of Pasteurized Milk products in Virudhunagar District" fills this gap.

Objectives of the study

1. To study the occupation and opinion level of pasteurized milk in the Study area.
2. To analyze the respondents' opinion on types of pasteurized milk products in relation to sales.
3. To identify the brand preference factors of pasteurized milk in the Study region.

Research Methodology

Research Design

A research design specifies the methods and procedures for conducting a particular study. It is a map or blue print for which the research to be conducted. Descriptive research design has been considered as a suitable methodology for present study and for data analysis.

Sampling Design

The sampling design used was convenience sampling, which is a non-probability sampling method. The convenience factors were the availability and approachability of the respondents.

Results and Discussions

Buyer Occupation Level

Data was collected from buyer to identify the Occupation level and is presented as follows.

Table 1 Occupation level

Particulars	No .of Respondents	Percent
Business	20	20.0
Employee	61	61.0
Farmer	4	4.0
House wife	15	15.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Primary data

Chi-Square Analysis

The buyer occupation and their preference for pasteurized milk was tested by the Chi-Square analysis.

Testing of Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis H^0 : There is no association between occupation and preference for Pasteurized Milk products.

Alternate Hypothesis H^1 : There is association between occupation and preference for Pasteurized Milk products.

Table 2 Occupation vs Opinion of Pasteurized Milk Product

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	DF	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	18.729a	8	.016
Likelihood Ratio	24.342	8	.002
Linear-by-Linear Association	.489	1	.484
N of Valid Cases	100		
a. 10 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .56.			

Interpretation

The ‘p’ value that is Pearson chi-square test reads a significance level of 0.016%. This value of 0.016 being less than the significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is association between occupation and preference for Pasteurized milk product.

ANOVA

The analysis of variance, frequently referred by the contraction ANOVA, is a statistical technique specially designed to determine whether the means of more than two quantitative populations are equal.

One Way ANOVA

ANOVA technique is used when an independent variable is of nominal scale with more than two categories and dependent variable is metric or at least on interval scale. In the present study, one way ANOVA was used to analyse the relationship between types of Pasteurized Milk products and opinion of normal Milk products.

Table 3 Type of Pasteurized Milk and Normal Milk

ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3.057	2	1.528	2.009	.140
Within Groups	73.783	97	.761		
Total	76.840	99			

H0: There is no significant difference between the type of pasteurized Milk and opinion of sales milk products.

H1: There is a significant difference between types of pasteurized Milk and sales.

ANOVA table shows the results of overall analysis of variance including the variation between groups, within groups, total sum of squares and mean square. The F- Ratio for this analysis is 2.009 with probability of .140 at 5% level of significance (95% level of confidence), this analysis does not support the alternative hypothesis of difference in the sample means, that is, there is no association between type of pasteurized Milk and opinion of normal Milk products are high.

Factor Analysis

Factor analysis is a multivariate interdependence statistical technique is a data reduction tool. Factor analysis removes redundancy or duplication from a set of correlated variables. It is helpful in representing correlated variables with a smaller set of “derived variables”. Factors are formed that are relatively independent of one another. The present researches have applied the factor analysis. The objective of factor analysis is to find out the inducing factors to buy Pasteurized Milk.

Details of Input Data and Variables

As the first step, sample buyers 100 in number were requested to state to what an extent they strongly agree or strongly disagree with 23 statements relating to the buyer preference in Pasteurized Milk to measure the degree of preference. Likert type 5 point scale was used, strongly agree-5, Agree-4, Netural-3, Disagree-2, strongly disagree-1.

Testing for Appropriateness of Factor Analysis

The appropriateness of the factor model is tested before extracting the factors. The test statistics for sphericity based on a chi square transformation of the determinant of the correlation matrix. Another useful statistics is the Kaiser- Meyer-OIK in (KMO) test of sampling adequacy. Small values of the KMO statistics indicate that the correlation between pair of variables cannot be explained by other variables and that factor analysis may not be appropriate. Generally, a value greater than 0.5 is desirable.

The correlation matrix was examined carefully and the two tests, viz., Bartlett s’ test of sphericity and Kaiser –Meyer-OIK proved that it was judicious to proceed with factor analysis in the present study.

Extraction of Factors: Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

The objective of factor analysis is to find out the inducing factors to buy Pasteurized Milk. There are two main stages in factor analysis as the first stage, principal component analysis was used for the initial extraction of the factors, and PCA is a technique for forming a set of new variables that are linear combination of the original set of variables. The new variables are called ‘percentage component analyses.

Table 4

Rotated Component Matrix								
	Component							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
QUALITY	.924							
QUANTITY	.910							
CLEANLINESS	.904							
PRICE	.856							
HYGIENE	.844							
TASTE	.726							
PRODUCT INFORMATION		.863	-.134					
DELIVERY		.848			-.115	-.123		
HABITUALISED	.171	.735	.107	.412	-.121			.111
FAT LEVEL		.512	-.123		.159	.568		-.450
CHOLESTROL	.166		.889	.268	-.128	.188		.138
CALCIUM		.266	.773				.214	-.216
CALORIES			.202	.867		.129		
MINERALS		-.210	-.304	.703	-.166	-.402		.102
SUGAR		.240	-.450	.589	.115	-.362	.137	-.103
VITAMIN	-.113	.146			-.888			
PRODUCT KNOWLEDGE	.199				.855		.124	.170
PACKAGING		-.261	.249	-.137		.853		.117
NUTRITION	.158				.241		.897	-.149
MILK PROTEIN	.193	.159				.128	.767	.478
ENERGY		.136			.438			.810
GLUCOSE		-.552	-.478	.291		.498		.190
CREAM LEVEL		.425	-.730	.161			.141	

Source: Results computed through SPSS.

Component 1

- QUALITY
- QUANTITY
- CLEANLINESS
- PRICE
- HYGIENE
- TASTE

Component 2

- PRODUCT INFORMATION
- DELIVERY
- HABITUALISED
- FAT LEVEL

Component 3

- CHOLESTROL
- CALCIUM

Component 4

- CALORIES
- MINERALS
- SUGAR

Component 5

- VITAMIN
- PRODUCT KNOWLEDGE

Component 6

- PACKAGING

Component 7

- NUTRITION
- MILK PROTEIN

Component 8

- ENERGY

Table exhibits the rotated factor loading for the 23 statements (variables) have been reduced to Eight components factors, namely,C1,C2,C3,C4,C5,C6,C7,C8,.Based on the above rotated component analysis, the present researcher proceeded to name the factors. Accordingly the first factor was named “Quality cum Quantity” , the second factor was named “Product information and Delivery”, the third factor was named “Cholesterol and Calcium”, the fourth factor named “Calories and Minerals”, the fifth factor named “Vitamin and Product Knowledge” the sixth factor named “Packaging”, the seventh factor named “Nutrition and Milk Prottein”, finally the eighth factor named “Energy”.

Friedman S’ Test

The **Friedman s’ test** is a non parametric statistical test developed by the U.S economist Milton Friedman. Similar to the parametric repeated measures ANOVA, it is used to detect differences in treatments across multiple test attempts. The respondents were asked to rank the product features of pasteurized milk such as Density of Milk, Creaminess, Freshness, Calcium content. Here, Friedman test was applied to find the difference in the ranks given by the respondents. The procedure involves ranking each row (or block) together, then considering the values of ranks by columns.

H0: There is no significant difference in ranks provided by buyers on product features of Pasteurized Milk.

H1: There is significant difference in ranks provided by buyers on product features of Pasteurized Milk.

Table 4 Ranking method of Product features

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Percentiles
						25th
DENSITY OF MILK	100	3.18	1.132	1	5	2.00
CREAMINESS	100	2.38	1.117	1	5	1.00
FRESHNESS	100	2.90	1.235	1	5	2.00
HYGIENE	100	3.28	1.443	1	5	2.00
CLACIUM	100	2.97	1.389	1	5	1.00

Source: Results computed to the spss.

Friedman Test

Ranks	
Nature of milk	Mean Rank
DENSITY OF MILK	3.10
CREAMINESS	2.49
FRESHNESS	2.85
HYGIENE	3.38
CLACIUM	3.19

The buyer's most rank the hygiene factor (3.38) in Pasteurized Milk

Suggestions

- Milk firms are not offering any free or complementary products to the customer for milk purchase. If they provide freebies for milk purchase, there are chances to improve sales volume.
- New innovative practices should be invented to preserve the pasteurized milk for long hours.
- Milk firms should have propaganda for the adoption of hygienic production for quality practices in processing of milk. Its highlight in the advertisement may increase the image of the firm.
- Milk firm may ensure timely delivery of milk.

Conclusion

Milk plays the vital role in human development. India is the leading producer of milk in the world. Measures of brand preference attempt to impact the marketing activities in the hearts and minds of customers and potential customers. As brand preference usually indicates more profitability, it would improve the companies' financial performance.

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